

ABOUT THE LIFE AND CREATIVE WORK OF ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR SARVAR
AZIZOV OF KOKAND STATE UNIVERSITY

Nabiyeva Madinabonu

Fergana State University, Master's Department

Specialty: 70110601 – Music Culture and Art.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19858591>

Annotation. This article comprehensively describes the professional activities of Associate Professor Sarvar Azizov of Kokand State University and his contributions to the field of music.

The article also introduces methods and teaching materials that can be used in educational lessons.

Keywords: Sarvar Azizov, P. I. Tchaikovsky, J. S. Bach, music, piano, educational lessons.

Piano performance is considered one of the most popular forms in the art of music. It is well known that every nation has its own national musical instruments. Today, there are universal musical instruments that are widely popular among all peoples of the world.

One of these is the piano. Looking at history, the art of piano performance began to emerge and develop during the Classical period, when the piano itself was created. Johann Sebastian Bach, along with his sons and students, created the first examples of clavier music.¹

The history of the piano dates back to very ancient times, even to Ancient Greece. During the time of Pythagoras, the founder of the theory of proportions, there existed a musical instrument called the monochord. This instrument consisted of a long, narrow box with a string stretched over it. Since the box was made of special wood, it produced a loud sound with a distinct timbre.

The string was fixed to the box with a stationary bridge, and there was also a movable bridge that could be shifted along the string to raise or lower the pitch of the sound. Over time, additional strings were added alongside the original one. This instrument was played using a special plectrum, and sometimes the strings were struck with a small stick or hammer.

As centuries passed, the instrument gradually developed. The box became larger and took on a rectangular shape. A keyboard was added near the strings. Musicians began to play it by pressing keys, which activated metal pieces that struck the strings to produce sound. This instrument came to be known as the clavichord. It was placed on a table and played while standing.²

This article is about a dedicated and responsible teacher, a true specialist in piano performance — Sarvar Salimjon o'g'li Azizov. He was born on April 16, 1992, in the Rishton district, into a military family. Due to his father's profession, the family had to live in different cities. While raising two children, the family had no idea that their son would pursue a career in music in the future.

¹International scientific journal «MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH» VOLUME 2 / ISSUE 4 / UIF:8.2 / MODERNSCIENCE.UZ FORTEPIANO CHOLG'USI VA UNING TARIXI Ruyiyeva Ozoda Furqat qizi

²THE ORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES International scientific-online conference 154 FORTEPIANO MUSIQA SOZINING KELIB CHIQISH TARIXI Nosirov Laziz 202Nematulloevich Navoiy Davlat Pedagogika instituti "Musiq ta'limi" kafedrası

The teacher himself describes how he entered the field of music as follows: “One day, my father’s car stopped in front of our house gate. I was outside playing football with my friends. My mother got into the car with my younger sister, and I followed them. My mother was planning to enroll my sister in a piano class, and I became interested as well. At that time, I was in the 3rd or 4th grade. If I hadn’t followed them or had been stubborn, I wouldn’t be in this field or at this place today,” the teacher recalls with a smile.

He received his initial education in Jizzakh at the Specialized Music and Art School No. 2 named after Pyotr Ilyich Tchaikovsky, in the class of Murakayeva Fayziya Abdulhadiyevna. Due to his talent and excellent academic performance, Sarvar Azizov completed the 7-year program in just 4 years.

After graduating from music school, he was admitted with privileges to the Art College in Jizzakh. In 2011, he was accepted into the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, where he studied for four years in the class of Nargiz Shamilovna.

In 2015, after completing his bachelor’s degree, he was admitted with privileges to the master’s program.

Sarvar Azizov teaches practical and individual classes for students in the fields of professional education (instrumental performance) and “Vocal and Dance,” using modern teaching methods as well as advanced pedagogical and information-communication technologies. The subjects he teaches include “Piano (Organ) Performance,” “Chamber Ensemble,” “Study of Piano Repertoire,” “Contemporary Issues in Piano Performance Art,” “Organ Class,” “Interpretation of Piano Music,” “Methodology of Teaching Piano,” “20th Century Piano Technique,” “Study of Piano Notation,” and “Stage Performance Skills.”

In his lessons, he applies non-traditional methods of teaching to provide students with knowledge. By preserving the achievements of the Uzbek national school of musical art and approaching them creatively, he aims to educate specialists who are capable of elevating culture and art to even higher levels in the future.³

Conclusion

Through this article, readers can not only learn interesting information about the piano, but also develop a greater interest in music. It also provides a broad understanding of the brief biography, life path, and creative activities of the dedicated teacher Sarvar Azizov in the field of music. Furthermore, the methods and teaching materials proposed by Sarvar Azizov play an important role in enhancing students’ creative potential.

REFERENCES

1. International scientific journal «MODERN SCIENCE AND RE SEARCH» VOLUME 2 / ISSUE 4 / UIF:8.2 / MODERNSCIENCE.UZ FORTEPANO CHOLG’USI VA UNING TARIXI Ruyiyeva Ozoda Furqat qizi
2. THE ORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES International scientific-online conference 154 FORTEPIANO MUSIQA SOZINING KELIB CHIQISH TARIXI Nosirov Laziz 202 Nematulloyevich Navoiy Davlat Pedagogika instituti “Musiqqa ta’limi” kafedراس
3. Based on Sarvar Azizov’s personal information.

³ Based on Sarvar Azizov’s personal information